

ARTICLES AS A GRAMMATICAL SYSTEM IN MODERN ENGLISH

Khasanova Zarrina

Teacher of academic lyceum of Navoi state mining
and technologies University

E-mail: mskhasanova@mail.ru

Kiranova Nozima

1st year student of academic lyceum of Navoi state mining
and technologies university

E-mail: kiranovanozima@mail.ru

ABSTRACT

This article explores the role and significance of articles within the context of contemporary technological advancements. This study delves into how articles function as fundamental component of language structure and communication in the digital age. By analyzing the impact of articles on various technological platforms and applications. Through a comprehensive examination of the relationship between grammar and technology, this article offers valuable insight into the evolving nature of language use in the digital era.

Key words: articles, grammatical, function, feature of articles, word combination, definite, indefinite, concept, grammatical attributive.

An article is a word that combines with a noun to indicate the type of reference being made by the noun. Articles specify the grammatical definiteness of the noun, in some languages extending to volume or numerical scope. The articles in the English language are *the* and *a/an*. 'An' and 'a' are modern forms of the Old English 'an', which in Anglian dialects was the number 'one' (compare 'on', in Saxon dialects) and survived into Modern Scots as the number 'ane'. Both 'on' (respelled 'one' by the Normans) and 'an' survived into Modern English, with 'one' used as the number and 'an' ('a', before nouns that begin with a consonant sound) as an indefinite article. The word some is thus used as a functional plural of a/an. "An

apple" never means more than one apple. "Give me some apples" indicates more than one is desired but without specifying a quantity. This finds comparison in Spanish, where the indefinite article is completely indistinguishable from the single number, except that 'uno/una' ("one") has a plural form ('unos/unas'): Dame una manzana" ("Give me an apple") "Dame unas manzanas" ("Give me some apples"). Among the classical parts of speech, articles are considered a special category of adjectives. Some modern linguists prefer to classify them within a separate part of speech, determiners. In languages that employ articles, every common noun, with some exceptions, is expressed with a certain definiteness (e.g., definite or indefinite), just as many languages express every noun with a certain grammatical number (e.g., singular or plural). Every noun must be accompanied by the article, if any, corresponding to its definiteness, and the lack of an article (considered a zero article) itself specifies a certain definiteness. This is in contrast to other adjectives and determiners, which are typically optional. This obligatory nature of articles makes them among the most common words in many languages—in English, for example, the most frequent word is the.¹ Articles are usually characterized as either definite or indefinite. A few languages with well-developed systems of articles may distinguish additional subtypes. Within each type, languages may have various forms of each article, according to grammatical attributes such as gender, number, or case, or according to adjacent sounds. Article can be also thought of a special kind of adjective, because it combines with a noun and contributes to the meaning of the noun-phrase. Many linguists place the article in the category of determiners. M. Blokh in his book “Theoretical Grammar of the English Language” says “The article is a determining unit of specific nature accompanying the noun in communicative collocation.” The linguists L.A. Barmina and I. P. Verkhovskaya have the same idea about the article as a

¹ . <http://www.world-english.org/english500.htm>

determiner. They attribute it to a syntactic class of words called determiners which modify a noun. The dictionary of Thesaurus gives the definition of the word “article” as a determiner that may indicate the specificity of reference of a noun phrase. Webster’s New World College Dictionary refers to the article as used as adjectives. Also in this context we would like to add the words of the linguist B. Ilyish who devoted a whole chapter of his book “Stroi sovremennogo angliyskogo yazika” to the study of the article. He remarks that the article is usually a separate unit which may be divided from its noun by other words, chiefly adjectives.

So, we may conclude that the first feature of the article can be that the article is a determiner of the noun that refers to, that is why it can have some functions of an adjective and it is used as a separate unit. Another feature of the article is that articles, definite or indefinite, are traditionally considered to form a separate part of speech. V.L. Kaushanskaya in her book “The Grammar of the English Language” specifies the article as a structural part of speech. In E. M. Gordon’s book “A grammar of Present-Day English” we also meet the notion of a structural word as the linguist gives the following definition of the article: “The article is a structural word specifying the noun”.

According to these two definitions we can define the second feature of the article – it is a structural word. Judging upon the definitions given by the different linguists and the dictionaries listed above we can draw a conclusion and deduce a general definition for the article that would include all its features: An article is a structural part of speech, which is combined with a noun to determine it.

There are two articles in Modern English which are called the indefinite and the definite article. The absence of the article, which may be called the zero article, also specifies the noun and has significance. The indefinite article has the forms a

and an. The form a is used before words beginning with a consonant sound (a book, a table, a door). The form an is used before words beginning with a vowel sound (an apple, an hour, an aim).

For better or for worse, English is blessed with articles. This causes a considerable amount of confusion for speakers of most of the world's other languages, who seem to get on rather well without them. The good news is that English began dropping the complex case systems and grammatical genders still prevalent in other European languages a very long time ago. Now we are left with just two forms of the indefinite article (a & an) and one form of the definite article (the). Perhaps more than anything it is the transition from being a language with synthetic structure to one which is more analytic that has helped gain English the kind of unrivalled worldwide acceptance it enjoys today.

Although greatly simplified, English article usage still poses a number of challenges to speakers of other European languages. Let's compare the German sentence "как ботанист он любит природу" with the corresponding English one "Being a botanist, he is fond of nature". You'll see that English puts an indefinite article in front of a profession but German doesn't. Conversely, English manages without articles in front of abstract nouns like nature, where German needs a definite article.

Even between British and American usage one finds subtle differences in nuance or emphasis. For example, Americans usually say someone is in the hospital, much as they could be at the bank or in the park. To the British this sounds like there is only one hospital in town or that the American is thinking of one hospital in particular that he or she patronizes. The Brits say an ailing person is in hospital, just as they would say a child is at school or a criminal is in prison. This is because they are thinking more of the primary activities that take place within those institutions rather than the building in which they are housed. If, however, you are merely visiting one of these places, you are at the hospital, at the school or at the

prison- both British and Americans agree here that what we have in mind is the building itself.

These few examples serve to illustrate that there is more to articles than at first meets the eye. From whatever perspective you are viewing this page, we hope you'll discover that articles are actually precision tools that greatly contribute unique accuracy of expression afforded by the English language. Most article usage does in fact have a reasonably logical explanation. If this can properly grasped then non-native English can be made a lot less conspicuous and man.

First the good news: There only three articles in English: a, an and the.

There are two types of articles indefinite 'a' and 'an' or definite 'the'. You also need to know when not to use an article.

The bad news is that their proper use is complex, especially when you get into the advanced use of English. Quite often you have to work it out by what sounds right, which can be frustrating for a learner.

Indefinite articles-a and an (determiners)

A and an are the indefinite articles. They refer to something not specifically known to the person you are communicating with.

A and an are used before nouns that introduce something or someone you have not mentioned before: For example:

"I saw an elephant this morning." "I ate a banana for lunch."

A and an are also used when talking about your profession: For example:

"I am an English teacher." "I am a builder." Note!

You use a when the noun you are referring to begins with a consonant (b, c, d, f, g, h, j, k, l, m, n, p, q, r, s, t, v, w, x, y or z), for example, "a city", "a factory", and "a hotel". You use a when the noun you are referring to begins with a vowel (a, e, i, o, u)

Pronunciation changes this rule. It's the sound that matters, not the spelling.

If the next word begins with a consonant sound when we say it, for example, “university” then we use a. if the next word begins with a vowel sound when we say it, for example “hour” then we use an.

We say “university” with a “y” sound at the beginning as though it were spelt “youniversity”. So “ a university “ is correct.

Definite Article – the (determiners)

You use the when you know that the listener knows or can work out what particular person/thing you are talking about. For example:

“ The apple you ate was rotten”, “ Did you lock the car “

You should also use the when you have already mentioned the thing you are talking about. For example:

She’s got two children; a girl and a boy. The girl’s eight and the boy’s fourteen.

We use the to talk about geographical points on the globe. For example:

The north Pole, the equator

We use the to talk about rivers, oceans and seas For example:

The Nile, the Pacific, the English channel

We also use the before certain nouns when we know there is only one of a particular thing. For example:

The rain, the sun, the wind, the world, the earth, the White House etc..

However if you want to describe a particular instance of these you should use a/an.

For example:

“ I could hear the wind “ , “ There’s a cold wind blowing. “

“ What are your plans for the future? “ , “ She has a promising future ahead of her.”

The is also used to say that a particular person or thing being mentioned is the best, most famous, etc. In this use, the is usually given strong pronunciation: For example: “ Harry’s Bar is the place to go.”

“ You don’t mean you met the Tony Blair, do you? “